

Abstract. In this article we have described about the adjectives, examples and usage. The authors analyze adjectives that are typically feminine and nominative singular form. Research on the interference of Latin into English confirmed that 98% of all English medical terms have Latin or Greek roots. But we have seen that English has dominated in science.

Key words: descriptive, expressive, versatile, fundamental, compelling, innovative, unique, trustworthy.

Introduction. An adjective is a word that modifies or describes a noun or pronoun. Comparative adjectives are used to compare two things. They're usually formed by adding the suffix "-er" (or "-r" if the word ends in the letter "e"). For two-syllable words that end in "y," the "y" is replaced with "-ier."

Main body. Comparative adjectives can also be formed by adding "more" or "less" before an adjective that has not been modified. The "more" form is typically used for words with two or more syllables, while the "less" form is used for all adjectives.

Examples: *Comparative adjectives in a sentence*

Simon's essay is longer than Claire's.

The room is cozier with the fire lit and less cozy without it.

I have never met a more honorable person.

Superlative adjectives are used to indicate that something has the most or least of a specific quality. They're typically preceded by the definite article "the" and usually formed by adding the suffix "-est" (or "-st" if the word ends in the letter "e"). For two-syllable words that end in "y," the "y" is replaced with "-iest."

Superlative adjectives can also be formed by adding "most" or "least" before an adjective that has not been modified. The "most" form is typically used for words with two or more syllables, while the "least" form is used for all adjectives.

Examples: Superlative adjectives in a sentence

Even the greatest athletes need adequate rest.

All the courses were delicious, but the dessert was the tastiest.

Alicia is the most charming person at the party, but her partner is the least charming. Absolute adjectives

An absolute adjective is an adjective describing an absolute state that cannot be compared. For example, the word "dead" is often considered to be an absolute adjective because it's not possible to be "deader" than someone else.

However, actual usage varies, and absolute adjectives are often modified by words such as "almost."

Coordinate adjectives. Coordinate adjectives are two or more adjectives that modify the same noun in a sentence. Coordinate adjectives can be separated by commas or by the conjunction "and."

Conclusion. English has two articles: the and a/an. "The" is used to refer to specific or particular nouns; "a/an" is used to modify non-specific or non-particular nouns. We call "the" the definite article and "a/an" the indefinite article.

Here's another way to explain it: "The" is used to refer to a specific or particular member of a group. For example, "I just saw the most popular movie of the year." There are many movies, but only one particular movie is the most popular. Therefore, we use "the".

"A/an" is used to refer to a non-specific or non-particular member of the group. For example, "I would like to go see a movie." Here, we're not talking about a specific movie. We're talking about any movie. There are many movies, and I want to see any movie. I don't have a specific one in mind.

Abstract nouns represent intangible ideas—things you can't perceive with the five main senses. Words like love, time, beauty, and science are all abstract nouns because you can't touch them or see them.

Without a tangible frame of reference, abstract nouns can be hard to pin down with grammar rules. In this quick guide, we explain the basics so you can use abstract nouns with confidence.

Adjectives describe or modify—that is, they limit or restrict the meaning of—nouns and pronouns. They may name qualities of all kinds: huge, red, angry, tremendous, unique, rare, etc. Some adjectives describe qualities that can exist in different amounts or degrees. To do this, the adjective will either change in form (usually by adding -er or -est) or will be used with words like more, most, very, slightly, etc.: "the older girls," "the longest day of the year," "a very strong feeling," "more expensive than that one." Other adjectives describe qualities that do not vary—"nuclear energy," "a medical doctor"—and do not change form.

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